

EBFMC25-OP-24 · Working Women's Health: Preliminary Findings on General Health, Service Use, and Work-Life Balance

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study aims to investigate the associations between general health status, utilisation of preventive health services, and work-life balance among working women.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive epidemiological study was conducted with women aged 25–55 years who had been employed for at least one year. Data were collected through a structured online questionnaire including sociodemographic variables, general health status, preventive health service utilisation, and the New Work-Life Balance Scale. The scale comprises three subscales -private life, work life, and improvement- and is scored using a 5-point Likert-type system, with higher scores indicating better balance.

Results: A total of 180 employed women participated in the study. The mean age was 36.1 ± 8.6 years. Of the participants, 70.6% were married and 54.4% had at least one child. While 41.1% of participants reported using preventive health services at least once a year, 35% stated they never used such services. The mean total score on the Work-Life Balance Scale was 3.10 ± 0.68 . Subscale scores were: private life (2.77 ± 1.06), work life (3.84 ± 0.82), and improvement (2.94 ± 0.88). These results suggest that although women tend to have a more balanced work life, they face more challenges in the domain of private life.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that a substantial portion of working women underutilise preventive healthcare services and face difficulties in maintaining work-life balance, particularly in their private lives (Budak et al., 1991; Hacettepe University HISAM, 2024; International Labour Organization [ILO], 2024). Consistent with our results, studies observe that employed women generally utilize fewer health services (Alizadeh et al., 2023; Esin & Öztürk, 2005). For instance, a U.S. study noted that many working women struggle to attend routine preventive screenings because full-time work hours and inflexible clinic schedules conflict with healthcare access (Bonner, 2024). These results highlight the need for workplace health promotion initiatives, increased access to preventive care, and supportive policies to improve the health and well-being of working women.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Women's health, work-life balance, preventive healthcare

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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